

Initial LCA report for the BIO-CHP case study for socio-economic assessment

Deliverable D6.1

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D8.1 Project Management Handbook

<p> Deliverable title Work Package Lead beneficiary Due Date Actual delivery date Dissemination level Abstract </p> <p> Project Acronym Project Call Type of Action Project Start Date Project duration Grant Number </p>	<p> Initial LCA report for the BIO-CHP case study for socio-economic assessment WP6 UBB 31/09/2024 </p> <p> Public The first section of D6.1 provides a summary of climate change and global warming, including its causes, effects, main industrial contributors and potential mitigation strategies. The second part describes the LCA methodology considered when performing the environmental evaluation, while offering the main material and energy balance data. The third chapter focuses on the environmental performance of the MEA- and CaLby2030 CO₂ capture technologies integrated within a Bio-CHP plant, emphasizing the main LCA results. The overall conclusions are provided in the final section. </p> <p> CaLby2030 HORIZON-CL5-2021-D3-02-13 HORIZON EUROPE - Research and Innovation Action 01/10/2022 42 months 101075416 </p>	
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1 INTRODUCTION

1.1 Background

For thousands of years, human activity has been steadily changing the environment, although these changes have primarily been local. However, the massive amounts of CO₂ and other greenhouse gases (GHGs) released into the atmosphere as a result of burning fossil fuels have surpassed all of the improvements made during the Industrial Revolution [1]. Despite the fact that GHGs are essential to life on Earth due to how they assist with maintaining a stable temperature [2], higher concentrations in the atmosphere trap more heat, which eventually causes global warming and climate change [3].

Carbon dioxide is by far the most significant anthropogenic GHG, which emissions reached a historic 419 parts per million (ppm) in 2023, in contrast to 280 ppm registered in the 19th century. In addition, CO₂ emissions, which make up around 73% of total human caused releases, will continue to persist in the atmosphere for 200 to thousands of years [4]. Accordingly, the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC) predicts that the global surface temperature will rise by 1.5°C to 4°C over the course of the next century if significant global measures to reduce CO₂ emissions are not adopted. Climate change, hence global warming, will ultimately result in serious and permanent effects on both aquatic and terrestrial ecosystems. These consequences will include thinning glaciers and ice sheets, rising sea levels, severe weather events like hurricanes, droughts, and heat waves, as well as ocean acidification and deoxygenation [4].

The International Energy Agency (IEA) reports that even though power generation contributed 1.3% less CO₂ emissions in 2019, it was still the largest contributor, making up 41% of all CO₂ emissions worldwide. The most widely used source, coal, contributed 29% of these emissions, followed by natural gas (9%), oil (2%), and natural gas (9%) [5]. Apart from the GHG emissions caused by thermal and electricity generation, the industrial sector also releases substantial amounts of CO₂ emissions, as illustrated in Figure 1 [6]. According to the IEA, the industrial sector was responsible for about 37% of the total energy use in 2022. A primary cause of the growth in power consumption over the past ten years has been the steady production expansion in high-energy industrial processes consumers (such as iron and steel, cement, pulp and paper, etc.) [7]. Additionally, industry was responsible for an estimated 9.0 Gt of CO₂ emissions in 2022, which is about 25% of all GHG releases [7]. A large amount of GHGs are directly linked to the on-site combustion of fossil fuels utilized to generate electricity. Yet, additional CO₂ emissions emerge either from the primary manufacturing process as a by-product or through chemical reactions which take place and cannot be prevented (e.g., metallurgical processes, mineral degradation, etc.).

Figure 1. Industrial direct CO₂ emissions in the Net-Zero Scenario (2000-2030) [6]

Consequently, in order to avoid new CO₂ emission peaks and limit the continuously increasing GHG releases, it is crucial to decarbonize the industry and transportation sectors in addition to the heat and electricity production. A decrease in emissions from the heat and power industry may result from decarbonization and increased energy efficiency. According to the IEA, in 2020, the power industry was rapidly moving toward carbon neutral, with GHG emissions decreasing by around 3.3% as a result of the COVID-19 pandemic-induced drop in energy use, but mostly because of improvements in the generation of green energy [8]. Nevertheless, in 2021 the CO₂ emissions rebounded with an over 900 Mt increase (nearly 7%) compared to 2020 levels, resulting in a total of 14.6 Gt CO₂ [8]. In addition, in 2022, emissions increased by yet another 220 Mt, reaching a record-high of 14.8 Gt CO₂ [7].

1.2 Calcium looping carbon capture system

The industrial sector needs to adopt a number of measures to curb GHG emissions and move toward the Net-Zero Emission (NZE) Scenario, including increased material and energy efficiency, a more rapid switch to renewable energy sources, and a quicker integration of Carbon Capture Utilization and Storage (CCUS) technologies into the production process [7]. However, the integration of the CCUS systems is regarded as one of the most promising medium-term options for decreasing CO₂ emissions.

During the past ten years, amine gas sweetening has proved to be an efficient method for post-combustion CO₂ capture, as there are two large industrial facilities (Boundary Dam and Petra Nova) in operation [9]. Yet there are several disadvantages, such as high energy costs from solvent regeneration and rust-related equipment concerns.

Chemical-looping approaches make use of CO₂ sorbents or O₂ carriers as chemical intermediates to efficiently remove CO₂ while consuming the least amount of energy [10]. O₂ carriers are generally solid metal oxides that are built to carry out multiple cycles of oxidation and reduction in order to provide the oxygen required for fuel burning. Unlike traditional CCUS methods, changing the O₂ source can prevent the N₂ dilution of exhaust streams or the use of an Air Separation Unit (ASU) [11]. The scientific community refers to this kind of chemical looping technique as calcium looping (CaL). Here, sorbents—typically calcium oxide (CaO)—react with CO₂ to produce calcium carbonate (CaCO₃), which is then decomposed in a different unit to provide a nearly pure stream of CO₂ [11].

A CCUS system might greatly enhance environmental performance and contribute to achieving climate objectives at currently operating combined heat and power (CHP) facilities, according to scientific literature. The performance of a bio-CHP plant in a district heating system with CO₂ capture systems—which have varying energy needs per unit of CO₂ captured from the flue gases—was studied by Kumar and co-authors [12]. Another study carried out by Wang and collaborators looked at the range of potential CO₂ capture amounts, as well as the effect of CO₂ capture on waste-fired CHP plant performance [13]. Dong and co-authors suggested an approach centered around dynamic modeling to assess the possibility of national emissions reductions. Two operating modes were examined: first, maximizing CO₂ capture at the expense of certain energy generation, and second, maximizing CO₂ capture while keeping the quantity of electricity produced unchanged [14]. However, a Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) study may be used to quantify emissions with the ultimate objective of reducing the environmental impact.

1.3 Bio-CHP and LCA case scenarios description

The goal of the present deliverable is to evaluate the environmental performance of the CaL-based CO₂ capture system integrated within a Bio-CHP facility. The environmental performance of the calcium looping system will be compared to the conventional reactive gas-liquid CO₂ capture using Mono-Ethanol-Amine (MEA) as solvent in an effort to get a comprehensive understanding of the CaLby2030 technologies. Deliverable 4.3, prepared by the LEAP and POLIMI project partners, contains information about the key unit parameters, technical, and economic components of the MEA-based and CaL-based CO₂ capture systems. The Bio-CHP plant used as a reference for this project is operated by Grupo HUNOSA. It is a circulating fluidized bed (CFB)-based combustion boiler that was first assigned to burn coal which was sourced locally. This was later modified to utilize waste biomass co-combustion and is currently undergoing a retrofit to handle completely biomass input. The integration of the MEA and CaL-based CO₂ capture systems, respectively, within the Bio-CHP plant is illustrated in Figures 2 and 3.

Figure 2. Schematic representation of the MEA carbon capture system integrated within the Bio-CHP plant

It is worth mentioning the fact that the fuel utilized in the calciner is the exact same high-grade wood pellet that is used in the Bio-CHP boiler.

Figure 3. Schematic representation of the CaL-based carbon capture system integrated within the Bio-CHP plant

2 METHODOLOGY

As more environmental concerns and legislation emerge, environmental impact assessments are crucial for establishing a process or product's environmental footprint. Identifying and measuring significant emission sources, starting from raw materials' extraction up to final product consumption or end-of-life treatment, may assist in minimizing their impact. Therefore, environmental impact evaluation has become a crucial component of the European Commission's plan for sustainable consumption and production. In this respect, the LCA approach is one of the most intricate and well-known instruments for environmental evaluation.

Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) has become an important tool for decision-making considering that it is designed to evaluate the environmental impact of each particular system in order to promote the most sustainable alternative among several options. In addition, LCA has been widely used in sustainable production of green fuels and biomaterials, environmental product declarations (EPD), and product development [15]. Moreover, this environmental assessment method is viewed as a complement to technological developments since it provides information by tracking and measuring a system's inputs and outputs, which helps prioritize areas for improvement [15].

Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) calculates the environmental and human health impact of a certain process or product by focusing on a specific function and taking into consideration all life cycle stages. According to the International Organization for Standardization (ISO) via ISO 14040:2006

(i.e., principles and framework) [16] and ISO 14044:2006 (i.e., requirements and guidelines) [17], an LCA study consists of the following steps: *Goal and scope definition*, *Life Cycle Inventory (LCI)*, *Life Cycle Impact Assessment (LCIA)*, and *Interpretation*. By providing more precise data sets or changing the purpose and parameters of the research, one can enhance the outcomes of LCA through an iterative process (see Figure 4).

Figure 4. Framework for LCA methodology

2.1 Goal and Scope definition

The ability of an LCA investigation to achieve its objectives depends heavily on how well defined and explicit its purpose is at the very beginning of the study. Important factors to take into account while establishing the aim of an LCA research include its purpose, the application(s) to be examined, the audience to whom the results will be communicated, and if the conclusions will serve as the basis for public comparison statements [16,17].

The goal of the current deliverable, part of the Task 6.1, WP6, is to quantify and evaluate the environmental performance of a Bio-CHP unit equipped with a CaL-based post-combustion CO₂ capture system. As previously stated, Grupo HUNOSA is in charge of the Bio-CHP plant used as a reference for this project. It is a CFB combustion boiler that was first assigned to utilize coal which was obtained locally. It was later modified to accept waste biomass co-combustion and is currently going through a retrofit to accept 100% biomass feed.

The environmental efficiency of the calcium looping system will be evaluated against the state-of-the-art in CO₂ capture, which is the reactive gas-liquid post-combustion capture using MEA as

solvent. The technical and economic aspects both of the calcium looping case and the MEA reference system were previously presented and discussed in detail in Deliverable D4.3.

The research is funded by the European Union under the Horizon Europe Framework Programme, Project name: CaLby2030 | Grant Number: 101075416. In addition, the project is supported as well by the UK Research and Innovation (UKRI). The study's target audience additionally includes members working in energy-intensive industries such as waste-to-energy, iron and steel, and cement manufacturing sectors. In addition, the study will be accessible to the general public (technical and non-technical), and the results can provide important insights for the decarbonization of hard to abate CO₂ emission sectors and decision-makers.

Following the definition of the goal, attention should be directed into the scope of the study. In the scope definition phase, the product(s) to be studied (i.e., the function of the system) are characterized, along with the functional unit (FU), the system boundaries (time and geographical as well as life cycle stages), methodological issues (i.e., allocation procedures if needed), impact categories to be included, impact assessment method, assumptions and limitations [16,17].

2.1.1 Function of the system and functional unit

The function the system has to be clearly specified as it serves as a starting point for setting up the FU and system boundary. The function of the investigated system consists of the integration of a calcium looping system for CO₂ capture within several sectors, including cement manufacturing plants, steel-making processes, or waste-to-energy power plants. The system's function performance is assessed and quantified by the FU, which also serves as a reference for the input and output streams. The reference flows of a given FU are the amounts of products or services required to properly complete the system function and generate that FU. For the current investigation, one ton of CO₂ captured was considered as the FU, thus all environmental impact categories will be reported to one ton of captured CO₂.

2.1.2 System boundaries

System boundaries are defined as the limits that separate the unit processes under study from the environment or other units. The processes that will be either included or excluded from the LCA study are in fact determined by the system boundaries. In line with ISO 14040:2006 [16], the system boundaries must take into consideration different unit activities and flows across all life cycle stages, such for example:

- Extraction and procurement of raw materials;
- Input and output streams for the main manufacturing/processing operation;
- Materials' distribution and transportation;
- Fuel production, as well as electric and thermal power generation;
- Use and maintenance steps;
- Waste and/or product disposal, including recycling/reuse of used products and energy recovery;

- Manufacture of ancillary materials;
- Manufacture, maintenance and decommissioning of capital equipment;
- Additional operations such for example lightning and heating.

There are four ways to define the limits of the system, depending on the goal of the investigation: i) cradle-to-grave, which covers process' stages from raw material extraction up to the end-of-life treatment; ii) cradle-to-gate, which involves steps from raw material extraction and production stage; iii) gate-to-gate, which solely covers the production phase; and iv) gate-to-grave which takes into account steps from both the use and end-of-use treatment, respectively.

The current investigation is a cradle-to-gate LCA study as it addresses the whole manufacturing process from the supply chain for raw materials up to the final product. Therefore, as presented in Figure 5, the following are included within the system boundaries: 1) *upstream processes*: electricity/fuel production, limestone extraction and transportation, MEA supply chain, oxygen generation from an ASU or as waste gas from water electrolysis, flue gases from Bio-CHP; 2) *main process*: CO₂ capture unit and compression and purification unit (CPU); and 3) *downstream processes*: disposal of waste materials, degradation of solvent, CO₂ transportation and storage.

Figure 5. System boundaries for the investigated scenarios

The geographical location and temporal system boundary are among the most significant factors to consider while determining the limitations of the system. On the one hand, plant location/geographical boundary stems both from market conditions and product definition. On the other hand, the temporal limits are much more difficult to define as certain stages from the product's life cycle need to be estimated (e.g., disposal or reuse) since they occur in the future. The geographical and temporal boundaries of the system under investigation presume that the plant is situated in Spain and has a lifespan of 25 years.

2.1.3 Impact categories and impact assessment method

As mentioned before, ISO 14044:2006 provides recommendations and guidelines for the appropriate selection of environmental impact categories. An impact category represents a collection of environmental issues (i.e., greenhouse effect, ozone depletion, human toxicity, etc.) of which the findings of the LCI study may be connected to. Conversely, an impact category indicator is a quantitative way to represent an impact category. A life cycle impact assessment (LCIA) method is derived from a set or collection of impact categories [18]. Many of these methods are already included in LCA software and can be referred to by many names, such as ReCiPe, CML, TRACI, Eco-indicator, or ILCD [19].

A conceptual framework that links the inventory data to environmental effects was established by the Life Cycle Initiative. First, at an intermediate stage, the inventory data with similar impacts are classified into an impact category called midpoint category or midpoint indicator. After that, a characterization factor is applied to each input and output flow to indicate its contribution to the midpoint category to which it is associated. Then, each midpoint category is linked to one or more damage categories that deal with the negative effects done to various protective areas (e.g., human health, damage to ecology, damage to resource availability, etc.); these categories are called endpoint indicators. Impact categories can thus be classified as damage-oriented strategies (endpoint method) or problem-oriented strategies (midpoint method) [20]. In the cause-and-effect chain, endpoint categories are positioned at the end and have greater uncertainty about the parameters but are easier to interpret. In contrast, midpoint impact indicators are positioned early in the chain and provide more accurate findings with less uncertainty [18].

Considering the goal of the present study, ReCiPe 2016 impact assessment method was utilized to perform the current environmental investigation. ReCiPe method is regarded as an improved version of Eco-Indicator 99 and CML since it allows the computation of both midpoint and endpoint level categories via a cause-and-effect chain. It was developed in 2008 through a cooperation between the Dutch National Institute for Public Health and the Environment (RIVM), the Dutch Institute of Environmental Sciences (CML) at Leiden University, PRé Sustainability, Radboud University of Nijmegen and CE Delft.

The ReCiPe impact assessment method takes three cultural perspectives into account in order to reduce the ambiguity generated by the transition from the LCI result to midpoint and from midpoint to endpoint indicators. Instead of illustrating human behavior preconceptions, each of these scenarios are utilized to group similar concepts. In addition, each perspective depends on a certain time period:

- Individualist (I) – based on a brief frame and upon the idea that technological advancement would prevent future issues;
- Hierarchist (H) – based on scientific agreement, it is regarded as the standard due to its balance and ability to account for both short and long-time spans;
- Egalitarian (E) – most conservative approach, assuming the longest and extended time-span and impact not entirely defined, yet little proof is provided.

The environmental impact categories provided by the ReCiPe 2016 assessment method are further detailed in Table 1 [18].

Table 1. Overview and description of the environmental impact indicators based on ReCiPe 2016 impact assessment method [18]

Impact indicator	Characterization	Main contributors
Global Warming Potential (GWP)	Anthropogenic emissions leading to an increase in surface temperature. Unit: kg of CO ₂ equivalents to air	CO ₂ , CH ₄ , N ₂ O, NO ₂ , CFCs, HCFCs, HFCs
Terrestrial Acidification Potential (TAP)	Increased proton levels in the natural soils due to the impact of acidifying contaminants. Unit: kg of SO ₂ equivalents to air	SO _x , NO _x , HCl, HF, HNO ₃ , H ₂ SO ₄ , H ₂ S
Freshwater Eutrophication Potential (FEP)	Excessive quantities of nutrients detected in the internal water ecosystem. Unit: kg of P equivalents to freshwater	Nitrogen and phosphorus chemicals
Ozone Depletion Potential (ODP)	Anthropogenic emissions that are causing the stratospheric ozone layer to thin. Unit: kg of CFC-11 equivalents to air	CFCs, HCFCs, halons
Particulate Matter Formation Potential (PMFP)	The ingestion of contaminants in the form of particulate matter (PM _{2.5}) by individuals. Unit: kg of PM _{2.5} equivalents to air	NH ₃ , NO _x , SO ₂
Fossil Depletion Potential (FDP)	Excess energy used for the extraction of one MJ, kg or m ³ of fossil fuel. Unit: kg of oil equivalents (with a lower heating value of 42 MJ)	Extraction of fossil resources

Mineral Depletion Potential (MDP)	Ore grade decrease. Unit: kg of Cu equivalents	Extraction of mineral resources
Photochemical Oxidant Formation Potential ecosystem (POFP _{ecosystem})	Increase in ozone concentration at the troposphere level. Unit: kg of NO _x equivalents to air	Particulate matter, NMVOCs, NO _x

Table 1. Continued [18]

Impact indicator	Characterization	Main contributors
Photochemical Oxidant Formation Potential human health (POFP _{human-health})	Tropospheric ozone population intake increase. Unit: kg of NO _x equivalents to air	Particulate matter, NMVOCs, NO _x
Human Toxicity Potential cancer (HTP _{cancer})	Risk increase of cancer disease incidence Unit: kg of 1,4 DCB equivalents to air	Chemical substances toxic to human health
Human Toxicity Potential non-cancer (HTP _{non-cancer})	Risk increase of non-cancer disease incidence Unit: kg of 1,4 DCB equivalents to air	Chemical substances toxic to human health
Water Depletion Potential (WDP)	Increase of water consumed. Unit: m ³ of water consumed	Use of freshwater

Decarbonising industrial processes with Calcium Looping

Freshwater Ecotoxicity Potential (FETP)	Relates to the possible harm of toxic compounds to the aquatic environment. Unit: kg of 1,4 DCB equivalents to freshwater	Toxic chemicals with a reported lethal concentration to
Marine Ecotoxicity Potential (METP)	Impact on the marine environment due to the increasing amounts of metals in the ocean. Unit: kg of 1,4 DCB equivalents to marine water	rodents and fish (e.g., Pb, Hg, Cd,
Terrestrial Ecotoxicity Potential (TETP)	Accounts for the potential impact of toxic substances on terrestrial ecosystems. Unit: kg of 1,4 DCB equivalents to industrial soil	halogenated organic compounds, pesticides or sewage sludge)

2.1.4 Assumptions used in the study

A lot of considerations must be taken while developing the LCA, particularly when factual data is either unavailable or nonexistent. This forces the LCA practitioner to rely on estimations and assumptions. Nonetheless, these presumptions may have a significant impact on the study's findings. Because of this, it is recommended to carry out a number of sensitivity analyses to ascertain how these estimations and assumptions affect the system's performance.

The following sections provide examples of the assumptions that were taken into account for each boundary limit (i.e., upstream, primary processes, and downstream processes) in this study.

2.1.4.1 Assumptions for the upstream processes

All relevant assumptions considered for upstream processes used in the CaL and MEA-based systems are listed in Table 2 and Table 3. The project partner CARMEUSE TECHNOLOGIES provided the data regarding the limestone supply chain.

Table 2. Assumptions considered for the limestone extraction and transportation

Process	Assumption		
Limestone extraction and transportation	Diesel consumption	0.36	l/t limestone extracted
	Groundwater	0.45	m ³ /t limestone extracted
	Surface water evaporation	8.12x10 ⁻³	m ³ /t limestone extracted
	Groundwater evaporation	2.12x10 ⁻²	m ³ /t limestone extracted
	Electricity*	2.17	kWh/t limestone extracted
	Transportation mode	Truck-trailer	
	Fuel used for transportation	Diesel	
	Distance	100	km

* Electricity is considered to be provided both from the grid mix and from installed PV panels

Table 3. Assumptions considered for the MEA production and transportation [21–23]

Process	Assumption
MEA production and transportation*	MEA is produced from ethylene oxide (EtO) and ammonia in excess. The reaction typically occurs in the liquid phase with 75 wt.% ammonia in water. The pressure needs to be sufficiently high in order to avoid the vaporization of EtO and ammonia. A distillation process is used to separate the unreacted ammonia and water, which are recycled back into the system. Any ammonia and water not consumed during the production process are considered as emissions to air [21]

In order to avoid the production of secondary and tertiary amines as by-products (e.g., diethanolamine-DEA and triethanolamine-TEA), an excess ratio of NH_3 : EtO of 10 : 1 is assumed to be sufficient to produce practically only MEA

Electricity used for multi-stage distillation process [22]	5	MJ/kg _{MEA} produced
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Emissions to air obtained from the production of MEA [23]:

CO ₂	3.13	kg/kg _{MEA} produced
CO	2.02	g/kg _{MEA} produced
Ethylene	0.17	g/kg _{MEA} produced
Ethylene oxide	1.64	g/kg _{MEA} produced
Ammonia	23	g/kg _{MEA} produced
Methane	6.71	g/kg _{MEA} produced
NMVOC	2.02	g/kg _{MEA} produced
NO _x	7.32	g/kg _{MEA} produced
PM 2.5 µm	7.27	g/kg _{MEA} produced
PM 10 µm	0.463	g/kg _{MEA} produced
PM > 10 µm	0.785	g/kg _{MEA} produced
SO ₂	8.66	g/kg _{MEA} produced

Transportation mode	Rail using cargo train	
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Fuel used for transportation	Diesel/Electricity	
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Distance (Germany to Spain)	2000	km
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* GaBi pre-defined processes were used for the production of ethylene oxide (obtained by oxidation of ethylene with air) and ammonia (produced by the Haber-Bosch process). The MEA supplier was considered the BASF in Germany

2.1.4.2 Assumptions for the main processes

The project partner LEAP performed modeling and simulation work that produced the data for the primary processes (i.e., MEA and CaL CO₂ capture for Bio-CHP), denoted by the system boundaries, and which were described in a prior release (i.e., Deliverable 4.3). The following primary assumptions are taken into account for the reactive gas liquid (i.e., MEA as solvent) and calcium looping processes used for post-combustion CO₂ capture from a Bio-CHP plant:

- 8000 operating hours per year where assumed (as specified in Deliverable 4.3 provided by LEAP and POLIMI);
- The CaL and MEA CO₂ capture systems are located downstream of the Bio-CHP power plant, after the flue gas treatment plant;
- The steam required for solvent regeneration (in the case of MEA capture system) is supplied by steam turbine bleeding directly from the power plant. This results in a gross electric

power loss in the steam turbine of about 7.1 MW_e (as specified in Deliverable 4.3 provided by LEAP and POLIMI);

- Oxygen used for combustion in the calciner comes from a cryogenic ASU, with an energy consumption of 240-250 kWh_e/t_{CO2} produced (as specified in Deliverable 4.3 provided by LEAP and POLIMI);
- The net electricity produced by the CaL capture system is about 11.5 MW_e (as specified in Deliverable 4.3 provided by LEAP and POLIMI);
- Wood pellets are considered to be used as fuel in the calciner;
- A make-up of 7.22 t/h of limestone was considered in the CaL system (as specified in Deliverable 4.3 provided by LEAP and POLIMI);
- In the case of the gas-liquid capture system, a MEA make-up of 1.6 kg_{MEA}/t_{CO2} captured was considered [24];
- Landfill disposal was assumed for the solid waste.

2.1.4.3 Assumptions for downstream processes

For the downstream processes, assumptions concerning the emissions of CaL and MEA CO₂ capture systems were correlated with the data reported in the previous Deliverable 4.3 and simulations provided by LEAP and POLIMI. Information regarding the degradation of the solvent (i.e., MEA) and other contaminants emissions due to chemical reactions are presented in Table 4.

Table 4. Assumptions considered for the MEA degradation and contaminants formation

Process	Assumption												
MEA degradation	<p>For the degradation of MEA, only the oxidation reaction was considered. Based on experimental studies, the following degradation reaction was applied [25]:</p> $\text{MEA} + 0.33\text{O}_2 \rightarrow 0.6\text{NH}_3 + 0.1\text{HEI} + 0.1\text{HEPO} + 0.1\text{HCOOH} + 0.8\text{CO}_2 + 1.5\text{H}_2\text{O}$ <p>Only ammonia, formic acid, carbon dioxide and water were considered as degradation products of MEA. The other substances (i.e., HEI = N-(2-hydroxyethyl) imidazole and HEPO = 4-(2-hydroxyethyl) piperazine-2-one) were not found in the GaBi database.</p>												
Emissions of pollutants due to chemical solvent reactions	<p>The decarbonized flue gas to stack resulting at the exit of the absorber contains a series of contaminants derived from the chemical reaction with the solvent (i.e., MEA). According to the literature, the primary contaminants (scaled for the current process) are [26]:</p> <table border="1"> <tbody> <tr> <td>MEA</td> <td>3.626</td> <td>g/h</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Ammonia</td> <td>819</td> <td>g/h</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Formaldehyde</td> <td>0.499</td> <td>g/h</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Acetaldehyde</td> <td>3.675</td> <td>g/h</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	MEA	3.626	g/h	Ammonia	819	g/h	Formaldehyde	0.499	g/h	Acetaldehyde	3.675	g/h
MEA	3.626	g/h											
Ammonia	819	g/h											
Formaldehyde	0.499	g/h											
Acetaldehyde	3.675	g/h											

The project partner UCL performed modeling and simulation work that produced the data for the transportation of CO₂. Several viable aquifers have been identified in the North of Spain and reported as part of the CO₂StoP project [27], therefore the specific choice was based on the work of Sun et al. [28]. The closest accessible storage site is onshore, at about 200 km south from the Pereda plant, near Burgos, where the Hontomìn Technology Development Plant, a pilot CO₂ injection site currently in operation, is located. Alternative CO₂ storage solutions might be found offshore in the Celtic Sea [29]. In particular, the Kinsale Head Gas Field has been chosen in this study. Decommissioning of the site has been completed in July 2023 and Ervia is currently completing feasibility studies, while operational timeline was initially indicated as 2028-2032 in the Ervia CCUS Project Information Report. The assumptions considered for the three cases of transportation are presented in Table 5, including several details regarding CO₂ transportation distances.

Table 5. Assumptions considered for the CO₂ transportation

Process	Assumption		
CO ₂ transportation onshore (Case 1)	Onshore transportation via pipeline	270 ⁽¹⁾	km
	Electricity for compression /reconditioning	0.1	kWh/kg CO ₂ transported
	CO ₂ losses (pipelines, compressors and injection)	0.01	%
CO ₂ transportation offshore (Case 2)	Onshore section via pipeline	30 ⁽²⁾	km
	Offshore section via pipeline	1000 ⁽³⁾	km
	Electricity for compression /reconditioning	0.1	kWh/kg CO ₂ transported
	CO ₂ losses (pipelines, compressors and injection)	0.01	%
CO ₂ transportation offshore (Case 3)	Onshore section via pipeline	30 ⁽²⁾	km
	Offshore shipping	1000 ⁽⁴⁾	km
	Liquefaction energy	0.246	kWh/kg CO ₂ transported
	Boil-off rate ⁽⁵⁾	1000	kg CO ₂ /h
	Ships heavy fuel consumption	3435	t/year
	CO ₂ losses (pipelines, compressors and injection)	0.01	%

⁽¹⁾ The distance is calculated from Casal Borsetti (Ravenna) to Piacenza. Existing pipeline diameters in this corridor range from under 600 mm up to over 900 mm.

⁽²⁾ The distance is calculated from Hunosa's site to Gijón Port. Existing pipeline diameters in this corridor range from under 600 mm up to over 900 mm.

⁽³⁾ The distance is estimated from Thomas Zement in Karsdorf to each of the proposed Harbours for onshore pipelines [30]. Existing pipeline diameters in this corridor range from under 600 mm up to 800 mm.

⁽⁴⁾ Offshore storage is located off the coasts of Norway. The distance to Equinor Sture terminal is estimated from each port. The routes are based on existent navigation corridors [30] and distances estimated using Google Maps.

⁽⁵⁾ The CO₂ emission results from heating the tank during transportation, due to engine operation and other activities on the ship. Releasing the gas formed is necessary to prevent overpressurizing the tank

2.1.5 Limitations of the study

It is not always possible to account for all that was planned for the LCA, and it is frequently unreasonable to change the purpose and scope to accommodate the new data sets, therefore the limits in issue need to be addressed and justified [19]. It is recommended to mention these shortcomings in the goal and scope section or the interpretation section, for instance, if only older data sets are available for a particular study than initially anticipated, or if there are data gaps in the LCI for data representative to every impact category and these are therefore no longer included in the results [16,19]. To prevent misleading and confusing life cycle assessment (LCA) results, it is necessary to explicitly identify the study's limits before drawing any acceptable conclusions or suggestions that may impact decision-making.

We can list the following things as limits of the current LCA research since they are not included in the system boundaries:

- Decommissioning of the facility;
- Repair and maintenance activities;
- Building transportation infrastructure (such as highways, railroads, and ships) as well as transportation vehicles;
- Installation of unloading facilities;
- Human endeavors associated with labour tasks;
- High-magnitude, non-predictable, low-frequency occurrences (e.g., escapes, unintentional spills).

2.2 Life cycle inventory (LCI)

Life cycle inventory (LCI) follows the Goal and scope definition stage and emerges as the process of building an inventory of reference flows for a specific process or product. It involves precise documentation of all input and output streams, including resources, raw materials, different types of energy, and pollutants to the air, water, and soil [16]. The graphical representation of an examined product system is made up of small boxes that describe the many processes and show how they interact with one another using single- or double-sided arrows (see Figure 6). Every one of the above-illustrated boxes represents a unit process, and it could stand for a particular step in the production or processing of a certain product [31].

Figure 6. Schematic representation of a product system

According to ISO 14040:2006, a unit process is regarded as the simplest component of the LCI phase that needs input and output data sets. Consequently, a unit process is thought of as a “black box” that converts an input data set into a series of outputs. There is a vast array of goods that could potentially be used as process inputs, including waste products, chemicals, components, and natural resources. Following the same guidelines, residues and emissions to the air, water, and soil could be selected as well as process outputs in addition to the primary product, which may be a specific material or service. In general, all of these data is compiled and reported using a table format [31].

2.2.1 Importance of data sources and data quality

In compliance with ISO 14044:2006 [17], each particular data set may consist of a blend of measured, computed, and/or estimated data. As data quality is a key component of LCI step, all data should meet the following characteristics: coverage of time, space (geographical), and technology; precision, completeness, representativeness, consistency, repeatability, source, and data uncertainty. In order to confirm and demonstrate that the data quality standards are met, data validations must be carried out during data collection. Examples of this include mass/energy balances and/or comparative study of release factors [17].

The data sets included in the LCI stage can be classified either as primary or secondary data. Whereas secondary data refers to information obtained from modelling, computations, estimations, or scientific literature, primary data provides information gathered through on-site measurements, interviews, and surveys.

The current study has made use of both types of data. When information from project partners or simulations were unavailable, it was obtained through interviews, process modelling, simulation and scientific literature. Whenever possible, measurements were taken on-site to support the modelling process.

In order to address any questions or discrepancies with the data, data checks were carried out iteratively and were dependent on ongoing communication with the project partners. Regarding

the technical coverage and resource supply chain, the overall data quality is thought to be excellent and representative for the systems under investigation.

2.2.2 LCI for several sub-systems

Table 6 provides the most important data sets for the CaL-based process, while Tables 7 and 8 provide the LCI for the limestone extraction and transportations, as well as for the CO₂ transportation both onshore and offshore.

Table 6. Life cycle inventory for the Bio-CHP plant integrated with Calcium Looping CO₂ capture system

Process	Inputs	Value	Unit	Outputs	Value	Unit
Bio-CHP plant				Flue gas	3.01x10 ³	kg/tCO ₂ captured
				Ar	33.67	kg/tCO ₂ captured
				CO ₂	592.33	kg/tCO ₂ captured
				H ₂ O	218.32	kg/tCO ₂ captured
				N ₂	2x10 ³	kg/tCO ₂ captured
				O ₂	165.01	kg/tCO ₂ captured
Carbonator	Flue gas	3.01x10 ³	kg/tCO ₂ captured	Gas Output	2.48x10 ³	kg/tCO ₂ captured
	Calcium oxide	5.28x10 ³	kg/tCO ₂ captured	Ar	33.67	kg/tCO ₂ captured
	Calcium sulfate	2.98	kg/tCO ₂ captured	CO ₂	63.02	kg/tCO ₂ captured
	Silicon dioxide	103.45	kg/tCO ₂ captured	H ₂ O	218.32	kg/tCO ₂ captured
				N ₂	2x10 ³	kg/tCO ₂ captured
				O ₂	165.01	kg/tCO ₂ captured
				Solids carried with gas stream	36.07	kg/tCO ₂ captured
			CaCO ₃	6.02	kg/tCO ₂ captured	

Decarbonising industrial processes with Calcium Looping

				CaO	19.69	kg/tCO ₂ captured
				CaSO ₄	1.49x10 ⁻²	kg/tCO ₂ captured
				SiO ₂	10.34	kg/tCO ₂ captured
				Separated solids	5.88x10 ³	kg/tCO ₂ captured
				CaCO ₃	1.2x10 ³	kg/tCO ₂ captured
				CaO	4.59x10 ³	kg/tCO ₂ captured
				CaSO ₄	2.97	kg/tCO ₂ captured
				SiO ₂	93.10	kg/tCO ₂ captured
	Carbonator cyclone gas output	2.48x10 ³	kg/tCO ₂ captured	Solids to landfill	36.07	kg/tCO ₂ captured
	Carbonator cyclone solids carried with gas stream	36.07	kg/tCO ₂ captured	Flue gas to stack	2.59x10 ³	kg/tCO ₂ captured
Flue gas to stack bag filter	Air	100.83	kg/tCO ₂ captured	Ar	35.01	kg/tCO ₂ captured
				CO ₂	63.02	kg/tCO ₂ captured
				H ₂ O	218.32	kg/tCO ₂ captured
				N ₂	2.08x10 ³	kg/tCO ₂ captured
				O ₂	188.35	kg/tCO ₂ captured
Calcliner	Solids from carbonator	5.88x10 ³	kg/tCO ₂ captured	CO ₂ gas output	2.1x10 ³	kg/tCO ₂ captured

Decarbonising industrial processes with Calcium Looping

	Recirculated gas	778.21	kg/t _{CO2 captured}	Solids in gas	33.73	kg/t _{CO2 captured}
	Recirculated solid	12.52	kg/t _{CO2 captured}	Solids to carbonator	5.39x10 ³	kg/t _{CO2 captured}
	Oxygen from ASU (95 %vol. O ₂)	446.91	kg/t _{CO2 captured}	Purge	13.48	kg/t _{CO2 captured}
	Calcium carbonate make-up	121.24	kg/t _{CO2 captured}			
	Fuel – wood pellets	291.67	kg/t _{CO2 captured}			
CO ₂ to compression bag filter	CO ₂ gas stream from calciner	1.32x10 ³	kg/t _{CO2 captured}	CO ₂ to compression	1.4x10 ³	kg/t _{CO2 captured}
	Solids in gas	21.21	kg/t _{CO2 captured}	Solids to landfill	21.21	kg/t _{CO2 captured}
	Air	85.21	kg/t _{CO2 captured}			
CO ₂ compression and purification system (CPU)	CO ₂ to compression	1.4x10 ³	kg/t _{CO2 captured}	CO ₂ captured rich gas to storage	1x10 ³	kg/t _{CO2 captured}
				Wastewater	158.11	kg/t _{CO2 captured}
				Vent gasses	245.45	kg/t _{CO2 captured}
CaL Net electricity output				Net electricity	193.38	kW/t _{CO2 captured}

Table 7. Life cycle inventory for the limestone extraction and transportation

Process	Inputs	Value	Unit	Outputs	Value	Unit
Limestone extraction and transportation	Electricity	0.35	MJ/tCO ₂ captured	Limestone	121.24	kg/tCO ₂ captured
	Water	5.82x10 ⁻²	kg/tCO ₂ captured	Suspended solids	6.94x10 ⁻⁷	kg/tCO ₂ captured
	Diesel (extraction + transportation)	0.30	kg/tCO ₂ captured	CO ₂	0.17	kg/tCO ₂ captured
				CH ₄	2x10 ⁻⁴	kg/tCO ₂ captured
				N ₂ O	1.32x10 ⁻³	kg/tCO ₂ captured
				Hydrocarbons	1.55x10 ⁻⁸	kg/tCO ₂ captured

Table 8. Life cycle inventory for the transportation of CO₂ onshore and offshore

Process	Inputs	Value	Unit	Outputs	Value	Unit
CO ₂ transportation onshore (Case 1)	Electricity	360	MJ/t _{CO₂ captured}	CO ₂ to injection onshore	999.9	kg/t _{CO₂ captured}
	CO ₂ captured	1x10 ³	kg/t _{CO₂ captured}	CO ₂ emissions to atmosphere	0.1	kg/t _{CO₂ captured}
CO ₂ transportation offshore (Case 2)	Electricity	719.96	MJ/t _{CO₂ captured}	CO ₂ to injection offshore	999.8	kg/t _{CO₂ captured}
	CO ₂ captured	1x10 ³	kg/t _{CO₂ captured}	CO ₂ emissions to atmosphere	0.2	kg/t _{CO₂ captured}
CO ₂ transportation offshore (Case 3)	Electricity	885.60	MJ/t _{CO₂ captured}	CO ₂ to injection offshore	921.09	kg/t _{CO₂ captured}
	Heavy fuel	123.67	kg/t _{CO₂ captured}	CO ₂ emissions to atmosphere	189.15	kg/t _{CO₂ captured}
	CO ₂ captured	1x10 ³	kg/t _{CO₂ captured}			

2.3 Life cycle impact assessment (LCIA)

The goal of the Life Cycle Impact Assessment (LCIA) step is to establish a link between the elementary flows of the system and any potential impacts on the environment. Given that the LCI step includes a wide variety of input and output flows (such as resources, emissions, and others), the LCIA phase translates the reference flows into environmental impact categories.

Regarding well-known and straightforward effect indicators, all inventory results are pre-categorized to pre-selected impact categories that are already included in a number of LCA software applications (e.g., SimaPRO, LCA for Experts, etc.), and for which characterization factors have already been determined.

To carry out the current study, LCA for Experts was chosen as the LCA software application. The LCA for Experts instrument, designed by the German company called PE International, has all the necessary components to model commodities and systems from a life cycle perspective. The software has access to environmental databases that cover a broad range of customer needs, such as waste treatment, product transportation, fuel and electricity generation and utilization, and material development.

LCA for Experts comes as a modular tool with a parameterized architecture. This instrument supports LCA studies that adhere to ISO 14040:2006 and ISO 14044:2006, as well as Life Cycle Engineering (LCE), Life Cycle Costing (LCC), Environmental Product Declarations (EPD), Product and Process Optimization, Design for Environment (DfE), Economic or Social Sustainability Assessment, etc.

3 RESULTS

3.1 LCA results and interpretation

The main goal of the interpretation stage is to provide recommendations and conclusions considering the limitations of the research, the issues identified in the LCI and LCIA results, as well as the goals and scope of the investigation [16]. The intended audience of the study should be able to easily comprehend the evaluation results when they are presented.

Table 9 presents the LCA results for the evaluated scenarios, taking into account the assumptions and limitations of the study.

Table 9. LCA results for the Bio-CHP scenario for MEA and CaL-based systems

KPI	Units	Base	CaL	Base	CaL	Base	CaL
		Case 1	Case 1	Case 2	Case 2	Case 3	Case 3
GWP	kg CO ₂ eq./tCO ₂ captured	248.43	180.84	274.06	206.47	561.08	493.49
FDP	kg oil eq./tCO ₂ captured	16.625	12.64	30.72	26.74	166.82	162.84
FETP	kg 1,4-DB eq./tCO ₂ captured	0.158	0.131	0.161	0.133	0.232	0.205
FEP x 10 ³	kg P eq./tCO ₂ captured	4.22	1.44	4.27	1.48	4.41	1.63
HTP _{cancer}	kg 1,4-DB eq./tCO ₂ captured	0.649	0.464	0.677	0.491	0.799	0.613
HTP _{non cancer}	kg 1,4-DB eq./tCO ₂ captured	62.68	55.20	62.91	55.43	91.22	83.74
MDP	kg Cu eq./tCO ₂ captured	3.35x10 ⁻²	0.15	5.94x10 ⁻²	0.18	0.11	0.23
POFP _{ecosystem}	kg NOx eq./tCO ₂ captured	4.48x10 ⁻²	-0.26	6.87x10 ⁻²	-0.24	0.23	-0.08
POFP _{human health}	kg NOx eq./tCO ₂ captured	4.35x10 ⁻²	-0.25	6.70x10 ⁻²	-0.23	0.21	-0.09
ODP x 10 ⁵	kg CFC-11 eq./tCO ₂ captured	1.48	-5.41	2.49	-4.40	4.54	-2.36
TETP	kg 1,4-DB eq./tCO ₂ captured	14.07	-8.89	16.51	-6.47	52.34	29.37

As can be noticed from Table 9, the environmental analysis considered three cases based on different CO₂ transportation scenarios (i.e., Case 1: onshore transportation by pipelines, Case 2: onshore and offshore transport by pipelines, and Case 3: onshore transport by pipelines and offshore by ships). To ensure a fair comparison across the various scenarios, all environmental impact categories are reported to one ton of CO₂ that is captured. When comparing the three options, the first case scenario—which solely takes into consideration the onshore pipeline transportation of CO₂—yields the best results. At the opposite, the third investigated option exhibits the largest impact and this is due to the offshore transportation of CO₂ by ships. Of all the environmental effect categories, the FDP impact score in Case 3 increased the highest—nearly 13 times—when compared to Case 1. This is primarily due to the use of heavy fuel by ships. In addition, the GWP increased by about 3 times between Cases 1 and 3. When examining Base Case 1 (i.e., CO₂ capture by MEA) against CaL Case 1, one can notice that the CaL system exhibits the best results in ten out of eleven impact categories studied (i.e., GWP, FDP, FETP, FEP, HTP_{cancer},

HTP_{non-cancer}, POFP_{ecosystem}, POFP_{human-health}, ODP, and TETP). In contrast to Base Case 1, solely the MDP impact score is about 4.5 times larger for the CaL. Other environmental indicators present in between 1.1 – 2.9 times larger values in Base Case 1 vs. CaL Case 1, including GWP, FDP, FETP, FEP, HTP_{cancer}, and HTP_{non-cancer}. The next section highlights the main sub-systems that contribute the most to each environmental indicator in the best scenario (i.e., CaL Case 1).

3.1.1 Global warming potential (GWP) Indicator

Figure 7 illustrates a detailed distribution of the GWP indicator, thus indicating the sub-processes that contribute the most (i.e., Limestone supply chain, CaL-based CO₂ capture, and CO₂ transportation).

As shown in Figure 7, the CaL system has the largest influence, contributing by 84.93% of the total of 180.84 kg CO₂ eq./tCO₂ captured. CO₂ transportation ranks second with a share of 14.18%, which represents around 25.64 kg CO₂ eq./tCO₂ captured. With 0.89% share, the supply chain for limestone makes the least contribution. Upon further examination of the CaL system, the primary sources of the 160.81 kg CO₂ eq./tCO₂ captured are the vent gases from the CO₂ compression and purification unit (i.e., roughly 61% share) along with the flue gases to stack (i.e., 39% share). As observed, negative emissions are registered due to electricity generation throughout the CaL process (i.e., - 8.21 kg CO₂ eq./tCO₂ captured). It has been considered that the electricity may be supplied to the grid, removing the need for additional fuel (e.g., natural gas, coal, biomass, etc.) and thus cutting the CO₂ emissions. Solid waste disposal accounts for approximately 0.98 kg CO₂ eq./tCO₂ captured of the total GWP score. As previously stated, the onshore CO₂ transportation contributes by 25.64 kg CO₂ eq./tCO₂ captured; however CO₂ losses account for less than 0.4% of total value, the remaining of 99.60% being due to the reconditioning for the CO₂ injection.

Figure 7. GWP indicator distribution for CaL Case 1

3.1.2 Fossil depletion potential (FDP) indicator

The FDP indicator is related to the extraction of fossil resources. The contribution of each sub-process to the overall FDP value in the CaL Case 1 (i.e., 12.64 kg oil eq./tCO₂ captured) is displayed in Figure 8. Electricity generation and supply for the CO₂ reconditioning for injection ranks as the main contributor with 14.10 kg oil eq./tCO₂ captured of the total impact. Assuming solely the onshore transportation of CO₂ in Case 1, the power utilized for reconditioning is assumed to be supplied from Spain's grid mix. According to the LCA Sphera database [32], the following sources account for the majority of Spain's power production: natural gas (26.50%), nuclear (22.15%), wind (21.44%), hydro (12.93%), photovoltaics (5.96%), fuel oil (4.07%), hard coal (2.10%), biomass (1.73%) and waste (0.67%). Since the CaL system generates electricity through the use of biomass as fuel, it adds negative emissions to the overall FDP indicator (i.e., -1.80 kg oil eq./tCO₂ captured). Solid waste disposal and limestone supply chain contribute by 0.30 kg oil eq./tCO₂ captured and 0.35 kg oil eq./tCO₂ captured, respectively. Of the total limestone supply chain contribution, 16% are due to the extraction process, while the rest (i.e., 84%) are due to the limestone transportation.

Figure 8. FDP indicator distribution for CaL Case 1

3.1.3 Freshwater ecotoxicity potential (FETP) indicator

The potential impacts of toxic substances on aquatic ecosystems are linked to the FETP environmental impact indicator. The overall FETP value for the CaL Case 1 is 0.13 kg 1,4-DB eq./tCO₂ captured. As Figure 9 illustrates, the CaL system exhibits the largest contribution with 98.14% of total share. However, it can be noticed that wastewater treatment sub-process stands as the major contributor to the FETP with 0.14 kg 1,4-DB eq./tCO₂ captured. Following the same reasoning, the net energy generated by the CaL system has a negative contribution, as it eliminates the need to produce energy from other sources that would release harmful emissions into the environment. In addition, 1.70% share of the overall value of FETP is brought by the electricity required for CO₂ reconditioning during the transportation phase. In contrast, the supply chain for limestone has a far smaller impact—only 0.15%.

Figure 9. FETP indicator distribution for CaL Case 1

3.1.4 Freshwater eutrophication potential (FEP) indicator

The freshwater ecosystem's nutrient content, particularly in terms of nitrogen and phosphorus, is indicated by the FEP indicator, which is given in kg of phosphorous equivalents. As reported, for the CaL Case 1, the total score in terms of FEP is $1.44 \cdot 10^{-3}$ kg P eq./tCO₂ captured. The overall distribution of the FEP impact category is shown in Figure 10. Wastewater treatment process ranks first with the largest contribution, $3.79 \cdot 10^{-3}$ kg P eq./tCO₂ captured. Conversely, negative contributions of $2.40 \cdot 10^{-3}$ kg P eq./tCO₂ captured are due to the electricity production through the CaL system. With contributions to the overall FEP value of 3.09% and 0.33%, respectively, the two sub-systems—the CO₂ transportation and the limestone supply chain—exhibit a considerably lesser impact.

Figure 10. FEP indicator distribution for CaL Case 1

3.1.5 Human toxicity potential cancer (HTP_{cancer}) indicator

Figure 11 displays the primary contributing sub-systems to the overall HTP_{cancer} indicator, which measures the potential harm of a substance with regards to cancer. As reported in Table 9, the total impact value of the HTP_{cancer} indicator for CaL Case 1 is 0.46 kg 1,4-DB eq./tCO₂ captured. The CaL system accounts for 94.01% share of the total contribution, while the CO₂ transportation ranks second with 5.93% share. At just 0.06%, the limestone supply chain contributes the least to the overall value of HTP_{cancer}. From the CaL system, the HTP_{cancer} category is most influenced by the wastewater treatment process, which contributes by 0.56 kg 1,4-DB eq./tCO₂ captured. The CaL system adds a negative contribution (i.e., -0.12 kg 1,4-DB eq./tCO₂ captured) to the overall HTP_{cancer} impact indicator as it generates electricity. Due to the electricity used within the reconditioning process, the CO₂ transportation contributes by $2.75 \cdot 10^{-2}$ kg 1,4-DB eq./tCO₂ captured to the total score. Solid waste disposal, limestone transportation and limestone extraction, each present a significantly lower influence (i.e., $2.65 \cdot 10^{-4}$ kg 1,4-DB eq./tCO₂ captured, $2.50 \cdot 10^{-4}$ kg 1,4-DB eq./tCO₂ captured, and $0.47 \cdot 10^{-4}$ kg 1,4-DB eq./tCO₂ captured).

Figure 11. HTP_{cancer} indicator distribution for CaL Case 1

3.1.6 Human toxicity potential non-cancer ($HTP_{non-cancer}$) indicator

Toxic substances may be examined for their effects on human health without causing cancer by using the $HTP_{non-cancer}$. For CaL Case 1, the overall $HTP_{non-cancer}$ value is 55.20 kg 1,4-DB eq./tCO₂ captured. Figure 12 displays the $HTP_{non-cancer}$ distribution in order to highlight the sub-systems that exhibit the highest influence. As can be observed, the CaL CO₂ capture system ranks first with 99.39% share of the overall impact. The contributions of limestone supply chain and CO₂ transportation are 0.42% and 0.19%, respectively. Looking at the CaL sub-system, the wastewater treatment process makes the most contribution (i.e., 56.71 kg 1,4-DB eq./tCO₂ captured). Similarly to previously discussed impact categories, the negative -1.90 kg 1,4-DB eq./tCO₂ captured contribution is due to the electricity generated. Solid waste disposal adds $5.58 \cdot 10^{-2}$ kg 1,4-DB eq./tCO₂ captured to the total value of $HTP_{non-cancer}$ indicator.

Figure 12. $HTP_{non-cancer}$ indicator distribution for CaL Case 1

3.1.7 Mineral depletion potential (MDP) indicator

The MDP indicator illustrates how the process contributes to the reduction in ore grades. Figure 13 displays the contributions of sub-processes to the MDP indicator. For CaL Case 1, the overall value of the MDP environmental impact indicator is $0.15 \text{ kg Cu eq./tCO}_2 \text{ captured}$, as shown in Table 9. The CaL system accounts for approximately 82% share of the overall MDP impact score, while the CO₂ transportation ranks second with a contribution of nearly 17%. At just 1.32% share, the supply chain for limestone makes the least contribution. If examining more closely the CaL process, the largest contribution (i.e., $0.40 \text{ kg Cu eq./tCO}_2 \text{ captured}$) is determined by the solid waste disposal. With $-0.27 \text{ kg Cu eq./tCO}_2 \text{ captured}$, the power generated by the CaL process makes a negative contribution to the overall MDP score. The negative number shows that mineral resources are conserved and do not need to be used to generate the amount of power produced by the CaL system (i.e., $193.38 \text{ kWh/tCO}_2 \text{ captured}$). The CO₂ transport process contributes with $2.58 \cdot 10^{-2} \text{ kg Cu eq./tCO}_2 \text{ captured}$ due to electricity demand, while limestone extraction and transportation show a significantly lower contribution (i.e., $0.30 \cdot 10^{-3}$ and $1.72 \cdot 10^{-3} \text{ kg Cu eq./tCO}_2 \text{ captured}$, respectively).

Figure 13. MDP indicator distribution for CaL Case 1

3.1.8 Photochemical ozone formation potential ecosystem (POFP_{ecosystem}) indicator

The total impact for the POFP_{ecosystem} category in CaL Case 1 is -0.26 kg NO_x eq./tCO₂ captured, as reported in Table 9. The POFP_{ecosystem} indicator refers to the increase in the concentration of chemical compounds such as ozone at the troposphere level. The POFP_{ecosystem} distribution and the influence of various sub-processes are depicted in Figure 14. The CO₂ transportation process accounts for $2.40 \cdot 10^{-2}$ kg NO_x eq./tCO₂ captured, whereas the limestone transportation has a contribution of $6.47 \cdot 10^{-3}$ kg NO_x eq./tCO₂ captured. The extraction of limestone impacts the overall score by $7.28 \cdot 10^{-5}$ kg NO_x eq./tCO₂ captured. However, the largest contribution, -0.29 kg NO_x eq./tCO₂ captured, comes from the energy generated from biomass in the CaL process.

Figure 14. $POFP_{ecosystem}$ indicator distribution for CaL Case 1

3.1.9 Photochemical ozone formation potential human-health ($POFP_{human-health}$) indicator

The increase in species concentration that influences the impact of tropospheric ozone pollution on human health is referred to as the $POFP_{human-health}$ impact indicator. Figure 15 shows the contribution of each sub-process to the overall value of $POFP_{human-health}$. The total impact score for the CaL Case 1 is $-0.25 \text{ kg NO}_x \text{ eq./tCO}_2 \text{ captured}$. With $-0.29 \text{ kg NO}_x \text{ equivalent/tCO}_2 \text{ captured}$, the electricity generated during the CaL CO₂ capture process makes up the highest contribution. This is followed by the CO₂ transportation process, which contributes $2.36 \cdot 10^{-2} \text{ kg NO}_x \text{ eq./tCO}_2 \text{ captured}$. Significantly lesser contributions may be seen when looking at the limestone extraction and transportation, and solid waste disposal.

Figure 15. *POFP_{human-health} indicator distribution for CaL Case 1*

3.1.10 Stratospheric ozone depletion potential (ODP) indicator

The ODP impact category measures the amount of anthropogenic emissions that contribute to the stratospheric ozone layer's reduction. As reported in Table 9, the total score of the ODP indicator in CaL Case 1 is $-5.41 \cdot 10^{-5}$ kg CFC-11 eq./tCO₂ captured. Figure 16 presents the contribution of the various sub-systems to the total value of the ODP indicator. Similarly to the previous impact categories, the net electricity produced by the CaL process exhibits the largest influence, contributing by $-7.97 \cdot 10^{-5}$ kg CFC-11 eq./tCO₂ captured. The limestone extraction and the CO₂ reconditioning rank among the main contributors with $1.45 \cdot 10^{-5}$ kg CFC-11 eq./tCO₂ captured and $1.02 \cdot 10^{-5}$ kg CFC-11 eq./tCO₂ captured, respectively. Limestone transportation and solid waste disposal present considerably less influence when compared to the other sub-processes.

Figure 16. ODP indicator distribution for CaL Case 1

3.1.11 Terrestrial ecotoxicity potential (TETP) indicator

The TETP indicator relates to the effect of toxic substances on terrestrial ecosystems and sediment environments. In the CaL Case 1, the TETP impact category has a total score of -8.89 kg 1,4-DB eq./tCO₂ captured. Figure 17 illustrates the sub-processes that exhibit the largest influence over the TETP indicator. The electricity produced and further used in the transportation of CO₂ brings a contribution of 2.43 kg 1,4-DB eq./tCO₂ captured, while the solid waste disposal adds 0.10 kg 1,4-DB eq./tCO₂ captured. Limestone extraction and transportation has a much lower contribution. Similar to the preceding impact categories, the TETP indicator's total impact is decreased by -11.51 kg 1,4-DB eq./tCO₂ captured due to the electricity produced by the CaL process.

Figure 17. TETP indicator distribution for CaL Case 1

4 CONCLUSIONS

The purpose of the current deliverable, part of the Task 6.1, WP6, is to assess the environmental performance of the CaL-based CO₂ capture system integrated within a Bio-CHP facility. The environmental performance of the CaL-based system is compared against the conventional reactive gas-liquid CO₂ capture using Mono-Ethanol-Amine (MEA) as solvent in an effort to get a comprehensive understanding of the CaLby2030 technologies.

The material and energy balances gathered through modeling activities, experimental operations, and relevant literature studies serve as a basis for the LCA calculations carried out in this deliverable. Therefore, the following processes are included within the boundaries of the system: i) upstream processes: electricity/fuel production, limestone extraction and transportation, MEA supply chain, oxygen production via ASU, and flue gases from Bio-CHP; ii) main process: CO₂ capture unit, compression and purification unit (CPU); and iii) downstream processes: waste disposal, solvent degradation, CO₂ transportation and storage.

The four LCA stages were covered by applying the standard LCA methodology, which consist of the following: 1) defining the goal, scope, and boundaries of the system; 2) performing an input-output inventory analysis; 3) assessing the environmental impact; and 4) interpreting the findings while offering recommendations for further improvement. For the purpose of improving understanding and transparency, comprehensive life cycle inventory data and specific assumptions for each process included in the system boundaries is given. The environmental

evaluation was conducted by applying the ReCiPe 2016 impact assessment method, while utilizing the LCA for Experts software v.10.8, previously referred to as "GaBi" software.

The environmental analysis focuses on three potential CO₂ transportation scenarios, one of which is onshore and the other offshore, in addition to the evaluation of both MEA and CaL-based CO₂ capture systems. The key environmental findings are outlined below:

1. When examining the CO₂ transportation alternatives, the first case scenario produces the best outcomes since it only considers the CO₂ transportation via onshore pipeline. On the contrary, the third scenario (i.e., offshore shipping of CO₂) has the greatest impact since additional electricity is required for the CO₂ liquefaction.
2. Out of all the environmental impact categories, the FDP indicator in Case 3 increased the most—roughly 13 times—in comparison to Case 1, and about 6 times when compared to Case 2. This is mostly because of the use of heavy fuel by the ships.
3. The CaL system performs better than the MEA-based CO₂ capture in ten of the eleven impact categories that were examined (i.e., GWP, FDP, FETP, FEP, HTP_{cancer}, HTP_{non-cancer}, POFP_{ecosystem}, POFP_{human-health}, ODP, and TETP).
4. In the CaL-based CO₂ capture approach, the carbon capture process ranks first with approximately 85% share of the total GWP score, followed by the CO₂ transportation with a contribution of 14.18%, representing around 25.64 kg CO₂ eq./tCO₂ captured.
5. The use of renewable energy sources could help lower the impact score of the FDP category, as the generation and supply of electricity for the CO₂ reconditioning process is the primary contributor.

NOMENCLATURE

GHG	Greenhouse gas
IPCC	Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change
IEA	International Energy Agency
NZE	Net-Zero Emission
CCUS	Carbon Capture Utilization and Storage
ASU	Air Separation Unit
CaL	Calcium Looping
CHP	Combined heat and power
LCA	Life Cycle Assessment
MEA	Mono-Ethanol-Amine
CFB	Circulating Fluidized Bed
ISO	International Standardization Organization
CFCs	Chlorofluorocarbons
CPU	Compression and Purification Unit
LCI	Life Cycle Inventory
LCIA	Life Cycle Impact Assessment
FU	Functional unit
GWP	Global Warming Potential
TAP	Terrestrial Acidification Potential
FEP	Freshwater Eutrophication Potential
ODP	Stratospheric Ozone Depletion Potential
PMFP	Particulate Matter Formation Potential
FDP	Fossil fuel Depletion Potential
MDP	Mineral Depletion Potential
POFP _{ecosystem}	Photochemical Oxidant Formation Potential ecosystem
POFP _{human-health}	Photochemical Oxidant Formation Potential human-health
HTP _{cancer}	Human Toxicity Potential cancer
HTP _{non-cancer}	Human Toxicity Potential non-cancer
WDP	Water Depletion Potential
FETP	Freshwater Ecotoxicity Potential
METP	Marine Ecotoxicity Potential
TETP	Terrestrial Ecotoxicity Potential
NMVOC	Non-methane volatile organic compounds
LCE	Life Cycle Engineering
LCC	Life Cycle Costing
EPD	Environmental Product Declarations
DfE	Design for Environment

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6 ANNEXES

The current Annex contains reports on the LCA for Experts (GaBi) diagrams for the CaL-based CO₂ capture system from the Bio-CHP plant, limestone extraction and transportation, as well as for the three CO₂ transportation scenarios.

CaL_Bio-CHP_linked_saled_1t_CO2_captured

Figure A1. LCA for Experts (GaBi) schema for the CaL-based CO₂ capture process

Figure A2. LCA for Experts (GaBi) schema for limestone extraction and transportation

Figure A3. LCA for Experts (GaBi) schema for the CO₂ transportation – onshore scenario

Figure A4. LCA for Experts (GaBi) schema for the CO₂ transportation – offshore scenario 1

Figure A5. LCA for Experts (GaBi) schema for the CO₂ transportation – offshore scenario 2

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